

DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF RP-HPLC METHOD FOR THE SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF SERDEX METHYLPHENIDATE AND DEX METHYLPHENIDATE IN BULK AND PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM

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ABSTRACT

An accurate, precise, simple, efficient and reproducible, isocratic Reversed Phase-High Performance Liquid Chromatography (RP-HPLC) method was developed and validated for the simultaneous estimation of Serdex methylphenidate and Dexmethylphenidate in bulk and combined pharmaceutical tablet dosage forms. Serdexmethylphenidate and Dexmethylphenidate were separated by using a Symmetry ODS C18 (4.6mm×150mm) 5µm Particle Size; Waters Alliance e2695 HPLC system with 2998 PDA detector and the mobile phase contained a mixture of Methanol: 0.1% Orthophosphoric acid (64:36% v/v). The flow rate was set to 1ml/min with the responses measured at 224nm. The retention time of Serdexmethylphenidate and Dexmethylphenidate was found to be 2.808min and 3.880min respectively with resolution of 5.68. Linearity was established for Serdexmethylphenidate and Dexmethylphenidate in the range of 20-100µg/ml for Serdexmethylphenidate and 60-140µg/ml for

Dexmethylphenidate with correlation coefficient 0.999. The percentage recovery was found to be is 100.30% for Serdexmethylphenidate and 100.21% for Dexmethylphenidate respectively. Validation parameters such as specificity, linearity, precision, accuracy and robustness, limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantitation (LOQ) were evaluated for the

method according to the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) Q2 R1 guidelines. The developed method was successfully applied for the quantification of bulk and active pharmaceutical ingredient present and in combined tablet dosage form.

KEYWORDS: Serdexmethylphenidate and Dexmethylphenidate, RP-HPLC, Validation, Accuracy, Robustness.

1. INTRODUCTION to HPLC

In the modern pharmaceutical industry, high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) is the major and integral analytical tool applied in all stages of drug discovery, development and production. It is ideal for the analysis of many drugs in both dosage forms and biological fluids due to its simplicity, high specificity and good sensitivity.

High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) is a technique that has arisen from the application to liquid chromatography the use of an instrumentation that was originally developed for gas chromatography. High Pressure Liquid Chromatography was developed in the mid-1970 and was improved with the development of column packing material and the additional convenience of on-line detectors. The various components of HPLC are pumps (solvent delivery system), mixing unit, gradient controller and solvent degasser, injector (manual or automatic), guard column, analytical columns, detectors, recorders and/or integrators. Recent models are equipped with computers and software for data acquisition and processing. The mobile phase in HPLC refers to the solvent being continuously applied to the column or stationary phase at a flow rate of 1-5 cm³/min. The mobile phase acts as a carrier for the sample solution. The chemical interactions of the mobile phase and sample with the column determine the degree of migration and separation of components contained in the sample. The mobile phase can be altered in order to manipulate the interactions of the sample and the stationary phase.

DRUG PROFILE

Drug : Serdexmethylphenidate

Synonym : Serdexmethylphenidate

Drug category : Agents that produce hypertension, Central Nervous System Agents, Central Nervous System Stimulants

Structure :

Chemical name/ Nomenclature / IUPAC Name : 3-([(1S)-1-carboxylato-2-hydroxyethyl]carbamoyl)-1-([(2R)-2-[(1R)-2-methoxy-2-oxo-1-phenylethyl]piperidine-1-carboxyloxy)methyl]pyridin-1-ium

Molecular Formula : C₂₅H₂₉N₃O₈

Molecular Weight : 499.520 g/mol

PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES

Description (Physical State): Solid

PKa (strongest acidic): 2.56

Log P: -2.7

Drug : Dexmethylphenidate

Synonym : d-threo-methylphenidate, D-TMP, Dexmethylphenidate, Dexméthylphénidate, Dexmethylphenidatum

Drug category : Serotonergic Drugs Shown to Increase Risk of Serotonin Syndrome, Serotonin Agents, Serotonin Modulators

Structure :

Chemical name/ Nomenclature / IUPAC Name : (R,R)-(+)-Methyl 2-phenyl-2-(2-piperidyl)acetate

Molecular Formula : C₁₄H₁₉NO₂

Molecular Weight : 233.311 g/mol

PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES**Description (Physical State):** Solid**pKa (strongest acidic):** 9.09**Log P:** 6.17**PHARMACOKINETIC PROPERTIES****Bioavailability** : 11–52%**Half-life** : 4 hours**EXPERIMENTAL METHODS****INSTRUMENTS USED****Table-: Instruments used.**

S. No.	Instruments And Glass wares	Model
1	HPLC	WATERS Alliance 2695 separation module, Software: Empower 2, 996 PDA detector.
2	pH meter	Lab India
3	Weighing machine	Sartorius
4	Volumetric flasks	Borosil
5	Pipettes and Burettes	Borosil
6	Beakers	Borosil
7	Digital ultra sonicator	Labman

CHEMICALS USED**Table-: Chemicals used**

S.No	Chemical	Brand names
1	Serdexmethylphenidate (Pure)	Sura labs
2	Dexmethylphenidate (Pure)	Sura labs
3	Water and Methanol for HPLC	LICHROSOLV (MERCK)
4	Acetonitrile for HPLC	Merck
5	Telma-LN 40	Glenmark

HPLC METHOD DEVELOPMENT**TRAILS****Preparation of standard solution**

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Serdexmethylphenidate and Dexmethylphenidate working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Methanol and sonicate to dissolve and removal of air completely and make volume up to the mark with the same Methanol.

Further pipette 0.6ml of Serdexmethylphenidate and 1ml of Dexmethylphenidate from the above stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with Methanol.

Procedure

Inject the samples by changing the chromatographic conditions and record the chromatograms, note the conditions of proper peak elution for performing validation parameters as per ICH guidelines.

Mobile Phase Optimization

Initially the mobile phase tried was Methanol: Water and ACN: Water with varying proportions. Finally, the mobile phase was optimized to Methanol: 0.1% Orthophosphoric acid in proportion 64:36 v/v respectively.

Optimization of Column

The method was performed with various C18columns like Symmetry, X terra and ODS column. Symmetry ODS C18 (4.6mm×150mm) 5µm Particle Size was found to be ideal as it gave good peak shape and resolution at 1ml/min flow.

OPTIMIZED CHROMATOGRAPHIC CONDITIONS

Instrument used	:	Waters Alliance 2695 HPLC with PDA Detector 996 model.
Temperature	:	38°C
Column	:	Symmetry ODS C18 (4.6mm×150mm) 5µm Particle Size
Mobile phase	:	Methanol: 0.1% Orthophosphoric acid (64:36% v/v)
Flow rate	:	1ml/min
Wavelength	:	224nm
Injection volume	:	20µl
Run time	:	7.0minutes

METHOD VALIDATION

PREPARATION OF MOBILE PHASE

Preparation of mobile phase

Accurately measured 640ml of Acetonitrile (64%) of and 360ml of HPLC Water (36%) were mixed and degassed in a digital ultrasonicator for 15 minutes and then filtered through 0.45 µ filter under vacuum filtration.

Diluent Preparation

The Mobile phase was used as the diluent.

VALIDATION PARAMETERS

SYSTEM SUITABILITY

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Serdexmethylphenidate and Dexmethylphenidate working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution).

Further pipette out 0.6ml of Serdexmethylphenidate and 1ml of Dexmethylphenidate from the above stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with Diluent.

PROCEDURE

The standard solution was injected for five times and measured the area for all five injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of five replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits.

SPECIFICITY STUDY OF DRUG

Preparation of Standard Solution

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Serdexmethylphenidate and Dexmethylphenidate working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent.

(Stock solution)

Further pipette out 0.6ml of Serdexmethylphenidate and 1ml of Dexmethylphenidate from the above stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with Diluent.

Preparation of Sample Solution

Take average weight of Tablet and crush in a mortar by using pestle and weight 10 mg equivalent weight of Serdexmethylphenidate and Dexmethylphenidate sample into a 10mL clean dry volumetric flask and add about 7mL of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. Filter the sample solution by using injection filter which contains 0.45 μ pore size.

Further pipette out 0.6ml of Serdexmethylphenidate and 1ml of Dexmethylphenidate from the above stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with Diluent.

PROCEDURE

Inject the three replicate injections of standard and sample solutions and calculate the assay by using formula:

% ASSAY =

$$\frac{\text{Sample area}}{\text{Standard area}} \times \frac{\text{Weight of standard}}{\text{Dilution of standard}} \times \frac{\text{Dilution of sample}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times \frac{\text{Purity}}{100} \times \frac{\text{Weight of tablet}}{\text{Label claim}} \times 100$$

PREPARATION OF DRUG SOLUTIONS FOR LINEARITY

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Serdexmethylphenidate and Dexmethylphenidate working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Preparation of Level – I (20ppm of Serdexmethylphenidate and 60ppm of Dexmethylphenidate)

Pipette out 0.2ml of Serdexmethylphenidate and 0.6ml of Dexmethylphenidate in to a 10ml volumetric flask and make the volume upto mark by using diluent and sonicate for air entrapment.

Preparation of Level – II (40ppm of Serdexmethylphenidate and 80ppm of Dexmethylphenidate)

Pipette out 0.4ml of Serdexmethylphenidate and 0.8ml of Dexmethylphenidate in to a 10ml volumetric flask and make the volume upto mark by using diluent and sonicate for air entrapment.

Preparation of Level – III (60ppm of Serdexmethylphenidate and 100ppm of Dexmethylphenidate)

Pipette out 0.6ml of Serdexmethylphenidate and 1ml of Dexmethylphenidate in to a 10ml volumetric flask and make the volume upto mark by using diluent and sonicate for air entrapment.

Preparation of Level – IV (80ppm of Serdexmethylphenidate and 120ppm of Dexmethylphenidate)

Pipette out 0.8ml of Serdexmethylphenidate and 1.2ml of Dexmethylphenidate in to a 10ml volumetric flask and make the volume upto mark by using diluent and sonicate for air entrapment.

Preparation of Level – V (100ppm of Serdexmethylphenidate and 140ppm of Dexmethylphenidate)

Pipette out 1ml of Serdexmethylphenidate and 1.4ml of Dexmethylphenidate in to a 10ml volumetric flask and make the volume upto mark by using diluent and sonicate for air entrapment.

PROCEDURE

Inject each level into the chromatographic system and measure the peak area.

Plot a graph of peak area versus concentration (on X-axis concentration and on Y-axis Peak area) and calculate the correlation coefficient.

PRECISION**REPEATABILITY****Preparation of Serdexmethylphenidate and Dexmethylphenidate Product Solution for Precision**

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Serdexmethylphenidate and Dexmethylphenidate working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette out 0.6ml of Serdexmethylphenidate and 1ml of Dexmethylphenidate from the above stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with Diluent.

The standard solution was injected for five times and measured the area for all five injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of five replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits.

INTERMEDIATE PRECISION

To evaluate the intermediate precision (also known as Ruggedness) of the method, Precision was performed on different days by maintaining same conditions.

Procedure

DAY 1

The standard solution was injected for Six times and measured the area for all Six injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of Six replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits.

DAY 2

The standard solution was injected for Six times and measured the area for all Six injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of Six replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits.

ACCURACY

For preparation of 50% Standard stock solution

Accurately weigh and transfer 10mg of Serdexmethylphenidate and Dexmethylphenidate working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution).

Further pipette out 0.3ml of Serdexmethylphenidate and 0.5ml of Dexmethylphenidate from the above stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with Diluent.

For preparation of 100% Standard stock solution

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Serdexmethylphenidate and Dexmethylphenidate working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette out 0.6ml of Serdexmethylphenidate and 1ml of Dexmethylphenidate from the above stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with Diluent.

For preparation of 150% Standard stock solution

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Serdexmethylphenidate and Dexmethylphenidate working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette out 0.9ml of Serdexmethylphenidate and 1.5ml of Dexmethylphenidate from the above stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with Diluent.

Procedure

Inject the Three replicate injections of individual concentrations (50%, 100%, 150%) were made under the optimized conditions. Recorded the chromatograms and measured the peak responses. Calculate the Amount found and Amount added for Serdexmethylphenidate and Dexmethylphenidate and calculate the individual recovery and mean recovery values.

ROBUSTNESS

The analysis was performed in different conditions to find the variability of test results. The following conditions are checked for variation of results.

For preparation of Standard solution

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Serdexmethylphenidate and Dexmethylphenidate working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution).

Further pipette out 0.6ml of Serdexmethylphenidate and 1ml of Dexmethylphenidate from the above stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with Diluent.

Effect of Variation of flow conditions

The sample was analyzed at 0.9 ml/min and 1.1 ml/min instead of 1ml/min, remaining conditions are same. 20 μ l of the above sample was injected and chromatograms were recorded.

Effect of Variation of mobile phase organic composition

The sample was analyzed by variation of mobile phase i.e. Methanol: 0.1% Orthophosphoric acid (64:36% v/v) was taken in the ratio and 69:31, 59:41 instead of 64:36 remaining conditions are same. 20 μ l of the above sample was injected and chromatograms were recorded.

Trial 5: (Optimized Condition)

Mobile phase : Methanol: 0.1% Orthophosphoric acid (64:36% v/v)

Column : Symmetry ODS C18 (4.6mm \times 150mm) 5 μ m Particle Size

Flow rate : 1 ml/min
 Wavelength : 224 nm
 Column temp : 38°C
 Sample Temp : Ambient
 Injection Volume : 20 µl
 Run time : 7 minutes

Figure: Chromatogram for Trail 5.

Table: - Peak Results for Trail 5

S. No	Peak name	R _t	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP plate count
1	Serdexmethylphenidate	2.808	65258	4326		1.08	5685.4
2	Dexmethylphenidate	3.880	8659854	659823	5.68	1.42	6895.7

OBSERVATION

From the above chromatogram it was observed that the Serdexmethylphenidate and Dexmethylphenidate peaks are well separated and they shows proper retention time, resolution, peak tail and plate count. So it's optimized trial.

Retention time of Serdexmethylphenidate –2.808min

Retention time of Dexmethylphenidate – 3.880 min

Table:- Results of method precision for Serdexmethylphenidate.

S. No.	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP plate count	USP Tailing
1	Serdexmethylphenidate	2.808	65898	4365	5682.2	1.08
2	Serdexmethylphenidate	2.808	65487	4375	5628.6	1.09
3	Serdexmethylphenidate	2.808	65324	4395	5649.7	1.08

4	Serdexmethylphenidate	2.808	65982	4328	5638.4	1.09
5	Serdexmethylphenidate	2.808	65248	4371	5698.3	1.08
6	Serdexmethylphenidate	2.808	65734	4391	5682.7	1.09
Mean			65612.17			
Std. Dev			304.8425			
% RSD			0.464613			

Table: Results of method precision for Dexmethylphenidate.

S.No.	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP plate count	USP Tailing	USP Resolution
1	Dexmethylphenidate	3.880	8659824	658784	6859.4	1.42	5.68
2	Dexmethylphenidate	3.880	8658547	657489	6824.6	1.43	5.69
3	Dexmethylphenidate	3.880	8659824	652368	6829.3	1.42	5.68
4	Dexmethylphenidate	3.880	8659875	658745	6892.7	1.43	5.69
5	Dexmethylphenidate	3.880	8658745	658213	6875.2	1.42	5.68
6	Dexmethylphenidate	3.880	8659862	652354	6859.8	1.42	5.69
Mean			8659446				
Std. Dev			623.2924				
% RSD			0.007198				

Table: Results of Accuracy standard values.

S.No.	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP plate count	Injection
1	Serdexmethylphenidate	2.860	65359	4358		1.09	5698.5	1
2	Dexmethylphenidate	3.949	8659825	659862	5.68	1.42	6859.4	1
3	Serdexmethylphenidate	2.860	65874	4395		1.08	5672.4	2
4	Dexmethylphenidate	3.949	8659875	653485	5.68	1.43	6824.2	2
5	Serdexmethylphenidate	2.860	65398	4382		1.08	5683.1	3
6	Dexmethylphenidate	3.949	8674587	6587458	5.69	1.42	6875.6	3

Table: Accuracy (recovery) data for Serdexmethylphenidate.

% Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (mg)	Amount Found (mg)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	35921.67	30	30.134	100.446%	100.30%
100%	70894.33	60	60.205	100.341%	
150%	105654.7	90	90.093	100.103%	

Acceptance Criteria

- The % Recovery for each level should be between 98.0 to 102.0%.

Table: Accuracy (recovery) data for Dexmethylphenidate.

% Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (mg)	Amount Found (mg)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	4276302	50	50.208	100.416%	100.21%
100%	8484717	100	100.148	100.148%	
150%	10160609	150	150.091	100.060%	

Acceptance Criteria

- The percentage recovery was found to be within the limit (97-103%).

The results obtained for recovery at 50%, 100%, 150% are within the limits. Hence method is accurate.

ACCURACY 50%**Figure: Chromatogram for sample concentration-50% Injection-2.**

Figure: Chromatogram for sample concentration-50% Injection-3.

Table: Results of Accuracy sample 50% values.

S.No.	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP plate count	Injection
1	Serdexmethylphenidate	2.816	35929	3896		0.98	4896.2	1
2	Dexmethylphenidate	3.893	4274645	578452	5.08	1.28	6895.1	1
3	Serdexmethylphenidate	2.816	35989	3958		0.99	4874.3	2
4	Dexmethylphenidate	3.893	4275698	586592	5.09	1.29	6826.7	2
5	Serdexmethylphenidate	2.816	35847	3874		0.99	4879.4	3
6	Dexmethylphenidate	3.893	4278563	586874	5.08	1.28	6895.3	3

Accuracy 100%

Figure: Chromatogram for sample concentration-100% Injection-1.

Figure: Chromatogram for sample concentration-100% Injection-2

Figure: Chromatogram for sample concentration-100% Injection-3

Table: Results of Accuracy sample 100% values.

S.No.	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP plate count	Injection
1	Serdexmethylphenidate	2.860	70989	4485		1.09	5698.8	1
2	Dexmethylphenidate	3.949	8488468	659822	5.70	1.43	6985.4	1
3	Serdexmethylphenidate	2.860	70896	4398		1.10	5786.9	2
4	Dexmethylphenidate	3.949	8478696	658952	5.71	1.44	6975.4	2
5	Serdexmethylphenidate	2.860	70798	4458		1.09	5864.7	3
6	Dexmethylphenidate	3.949	8486987	658754	5.70	1.43	6898.9	3

Accuracy 150%

Figure : Chromatogram for sample concentration-150% Injection-1.

Figure : Chromatogram for sample concentration-150%Injection-2.

Figure: Chromatogram for sample concentration-150%Injection-3.

Table: Results of Accuracy sample 150% values.

S. No.	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP plate count	Injection
1	Serdexmethylphenidate	2.824	105753	6528		1.24	6587.4	1
2	Dexmethylphenidate	3.914	12695265	752454	6.82	1.68	8695.3	1
3	Serdexmethylphenidate	2.824	105584	6584		1.25	6582.2	2
4	Dexmethylphenidate	3.914	12689898	752658	6.83	1.69	8759.6	2
5	Serdexmethylphenidate	2.824	105627	6539		1.24	6538.6	3
6	Dexmethylphenidate	3.914	12694574	753689	6.82	1.68	8698.5	3

LINEARITY

The linearity range was found to lie from 20-100ppm of Serdexmethylphenidate, 60µg/ml to 140µg/ml of Dexmethylphenidate and chromatograms are shown below.

Figure: Chromatogram for linearity concentration-20µg/ml of Serdexmethylphenidate & 60µg/ml of Dexmethylphenidate.

Figure: Chromatogram for linearity concentration-40µg/ml of Serdexmethylphenidate & 80µg/ml of Dexmethylphenidate.

Figure: Chromatogram for linearity concentration-60µg/ml of Serdexmethylphenidate & 100µg/ml of Dexmethylphenidate.

Figure: Chromatogram for linearity concentration-80µg/ml of Serdexmethylphenidate & 120µg/ml of Dexmethylphenidate

Figure: Chromatogram for linearity concentration-100µg/ml of Serdexmethylphenidate & 140µg/ml of Dexmethylphenidate.

Figure : Calibration graph for Serdexmethylphenidate.

Table: Linearity Results: (for Serdexmethylphenidate).

S. No	Linearity Level	Concentration (ppm)	Area
1	I	20	24759
2	II	40	47859
3	III	60	70898
4	IV	80	93985
5	V	100	116698
Correlation Coefficient			0.999

Acceptance Criteria: Correlation coefficient should be not less than 0.999.

Linearity Results: (for Dexmethylphenidate)**Figure : Calibration graph for Dexmethylphenidate.****Table : Linearity Results (for Dexmethylphenidate).**

S. No	Linearity Level	Concentration(ppm)	Area
1	I	60	4928578
2	II	80	6687842
3	III	100	8389878
4	IV	120	10085847
5	V	140	11769854
Correlation Coefficient			0.999

Acceptance Criteria

- Correlation coefficient should be not less than 0.99.

Table: Analytical performance parameters of Serdexmethylphenidate and Dexmethylphenidate.

Parameters	Serdexmethylphenidate	Dexmethylphenidate
Slope (m)	1163	84268
Intercept (c)	875.5	45373
Correlation coefficient (R^2)	0.999	0.999

Acceptance Criteria

Correlation coefficient (R^2) should not be less than 0.999.

LIMIT OF DETECTION

The detection limit of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample which can be detected but not necessarily quantitated as an exact value.

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times \sigma / s$$

Where

σ = Standard deviation of the response

S = Slope of the calibration curve

Serdexmethylphenidate

Result

$$= 0.97 \mu\text{g/ml}$$

Dexmethylphenidate

Result

$$= 2.06 \mu\text{g/ml}$$

QUANTITATION LIMIT

The quantitation limit of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample which can be quantitatively determined.

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times \sigma / S$$

Where

σ = Standard deviation of the response

S = Slope of the calibration curve

Serdexmethylphenidate**Result**=2.91 μ g/ml**Telmisarta****Result**= 6.18 μ g/ml**ROBUSTNESS**

The standard and samples of Serdexmethylphenidate and Dexmethylphenidate were injected by changing the conditions of chromatography. There was no significant change in the parameters like resolution, tailing factor, asymmetric factor, and plate count.

Variation in flow

Figure: Chromatogram showing less flow of 0.9ml/min.

Figure: Chromatogram showing more flow of 1.1ml/min.

Table: System suitability results for Serdexmethylphenidate.

S. No	Flow Rate (ml/min)	System Suitability Results		
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing	Retention Time (min)
1	0.9	5784.6	1.06	3.091
2	1.0	5685.4	1.08	2.813
3	1.1	5869.5	1.09	2.553

* Results for actual flow (1.0 ml/min) have been considered from Assay standard.

Table: System suitability results for Dexmethylphenidate.

S.No	Flow Rate (ml/min)	System Suitability Results		
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing	Retention Time (min)
1	0.9	6698.3	1.46	4.274
2	1.0	6895.7	1.42	3.886
3	1.1	6983.6	1.49	3.538

* Results for actual flow (1.0ml/min) have been considered from Assay standard.

Variation of mobile phase organic composition

Figure: Chromatogram showing more organic composition.

Table- System suitability results for Serdexmethylphenidate.

S.No	Change in Organic Composition in the Mobile Phase	System Suitability Results		
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing	Retention Time (min)
1	10% less	5895.3	1.12	3.301
2	*Actual	5685.4	1.08	2.813
3	10% more	5964.2	1.16	2.469

Table-: System suitability results for Dexmethylphenidate.

S. No	Change in Organic Composition in the Mobile Phase	System Suitability Results		
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing	Retention Time (min)
1	10% less	6785.2	1.46	4.344
2	*Actual	6895.7	1.42	3.886
3	10% more	6982.4	1.49	3.508

SUMMARY OF SERDEXMETHYLPHENIDATE**Table no: Summary of validation data for Serdexmethylphenidate.**

S.NO	PARAMETER	RESULT	ACCEPTENCE CRITERIA
1	System suitability Theoretical plates Tailing factor Retention time %RSD	5685.4 1.08 2.808 0.4	Not less than 2500 Not more than 2
2	Specificity a) Blank interference b) Placebo interference	Specific	Specific
3	Method precision (%RSD)	0.464	Not more than 2.0%
4	Linearity parameter Slope Correlation coefficient(r^2)	20-100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ 1163 0.999	≤ 1
5	Accuracy Mean % recovery	100.30	97 - 103%
6	Robustness a) Flow rate variation b) Temperature variation	All the system suitability parameters are within the limits.	

SUMMARY OF DEXMETHYLPHENIDATE**Table no: Summary of validation data for Dexmethylphenidate.**

S. NO	PARAMETER	RESULT	ACCEPTENCE CRITERIA
1	System suitability Theoretical plates Tailing factor Retention time %RSD	6895.7 1.42 3.880 0.3	Not less than 2500 Not more than 2
2	Specificity c) Blank interference	Specific	Specific

	d) Placebo interference		
3	Method precision (%RSD)	0.007	Not more than 2.0%
4	Linearity parameter Slope Correlation coefficient(r^2)	60-140 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ 84268 1	≤ 1
5	Accuracy Mean % recovery	100.21	97 - 103%
6	Robustness c) Flow rate variation d) Temperature variation	All the system suitability parameters are within the limits.	

CONCLUSION

The study is focused to develop and validate HPLC methods for estimation of Serdexmethylphenidate and Dexmethylphenidate in bulk and tablet dosage form.

For routine analytical purpose it is desirable to establish methods capable of analyzing huge number of samples in a short time period with good robustness, accuracy and precision without any prior separation steps. HPLC method generates large amount of quality data, which serve as highly powerful and convenient analytical tool.

The method shows good reproducibility and good recovery. From the specificity studies, it was found that the developed methods were specific for Serdexmethylphenidate and Dexmethylphenidate.

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